

Влияние безопасности образовательной среды на профессиональное выгорание учителей

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Профессиональное выгорание среди учителей является растущей проблемой в современном образовании, которая приводит к неудовлетворенности работой и сокращению профессиональной долговечности. Безопасность образовательной среды признается важным фактором, влияющим на благополучие учителя, однако ее связь с выгоранием остается малоизученной.

Цель данной статьи заключается в изучении связи между компонентами профессионального выгорания и показателями безопасности образовательной среды.

Материалы и методы. *Методы:* Опросник профессионального выгорания К. Маслач (MBI), метод оценки безопасности образовательной среды для педагога по И.А. Баевой, методы математической статистики (описательная статистика, корреляционный анализ Пирсона). *Испытуемые:* 42 учителя средней школы, женщины, отбор производился случайным образом из 2 регионов России, средний возраст: 42,2 + 13.09 лет.

Результаты. Было показано, что снижение безопасности образовательной среды приводит к развитию симптомов эмоционального истощения ($r=-0,609$; $p<0,01$) и редукации профессиональных достижений учителя ($r=0,414$; $p<0,05$). Было установлено, что эмоциональное истощение связано с: 1) отношениями учителей с их коллегами и начальством ($r=-0,405$; $p<0,05$), 2) уважительным отношением к себе ($r=-0,716$; $p<0,01$), 3) сохранением личного достоинства ($r=-0,548$; $p<0,01$), 4) защищенностью от насилия со стороны коллег и администрации ($r=-0,426$; $p<0,01$). Деперсонализация связана с 1) уважительным отношением к себе ($r=-0,395$; $p<0,05$). Редукация профессиональных достижений связана с: 1) отношениями учителей с их коллегами и начальством ($r=0,338$; $p<0,05$), 2) уважительным отношением к себе ($r=0,389$; $p<0,05$), 3) сохранением личного достоинства ($r=0,512$; $p<0,01$), 4) защищенностью от насилия со стороны коллег и администрации ($r=0,437$; $p<0,01$). Из показателей отношения к образовательной среде наибольшее влияние на выгорание оказывают: эмоциональный компонент (учителю больше не нравится его работа и поведенческий компонент (учитель хочет уволиться); когнитивный компонент (общее представление о работе как способе самореализации) не связан с выгоранием.

Заключение. На профессиональное выгорание педагога больше влияют неудовлетворительные взаимоотношения с коллегами и администрацией, чем взаимоотношения с учениками. Создание положительной эмоциональной атмосферы в школе и усиление возможностей учителей выражать мнения и принимать решения может помочь предотвратить выгорание и увеличить профессиональную долговечность. Эти выводы подчеркивают важность безопасности образовательной среды как ресурса благополучия учителей и удержания их в профессии.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

психологическая безопасность, безопасность образовательной среды, профессиональное выгорание, личность, педагогическая деятельность, личностный ресурс

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Impact of safety in the educational environment on professional burnout among teachers

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Professional burnout among teachers is a growing concern in modern education, leading to job dissatisfaction and reduced professional longevity. The safety of the educational environment is recognized as a crucial factor affecting the teacher's well-being but its connection with burnout components remains understudied.

This article aims at studying the relationship between the components of professional burnout and indicators of the safety of the educational environment.

Materials and methods. Design: correlational study Methods: K. Maslach Professional Burnout Questionnaire (MBI), Method for assessing the safety of the educational environment for teachers according to I.A. Baeva, methods of mathematical statistics (descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation analysis. Subjects; 42 secondary school teachers, women, random selection from 2 regions of Russia, average age: 42.2 + 13.09 years.

Results. It was shown that a decrease in the safety of the educational environment leads to the development of symptoms of emotional exhaustion ($r=-0.609$, $p<0.01$) and a reduction in the teacher's professional achievements ($r=0.414$, $p<0.05$). It was found that emotional exhaustion is associated with: 1) teachers' relationships with their colleagues and superiors ($r=-0.405$, $p<0.05$), 2) self-respect ($r=-0.716$, $p<0.01$), 3) preservation of personal dignity ($r=-0.548$, $p<0.01$), 4) protection from violence from colleagues and administration ($r=-0.426$, $p<0.01$). Depersonalization is associated with 1) a respectful attitude towards oneself ($r=-0.395$, $p<0.05$). A reduction in professional achievements is associated with: 1) teachers' relationships with their colleagues and superiors ($r=0.338$, $p<0.05$), 2) respectful attitude towards oneself ($r=0.389$, $p<0.05$), 3) preservation of personal dignity ($r=0.512$, $p<0.01$), 4) protection from violence from colleagues and administration ($r=0.437$, $p<0.01$). Of the indicators of attitude towards the educational environment, the greatest influence on burnout is exerted by: the emotional component (the teacher no longer likes his work and the behavioral component (the teacher wants to quit); the cognitive component (the general idea of work as a way of self-realization) is not associated with burnout.

Conclusions. Teacher professional burnout is more influenced by unsatisfactory relationships with colleagues and administration than relationships with students. Creating a positive school climate and strengthening teachers' ability to express opinions and make decisions can help prevent burnout and increase professional longevity. These findings highlight the importance of a safe educational environment as a resource for teacher well-being and retention in the profession.

KEYWORDS

psychological safety, safety of the educational environment, professional burnout, personality, pedagogical activity, personal resource

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INTRODUCTION

Professional burnout among teachers is a significant and growing concern in modern education, posing one of the greatest challenges to their mental well-being and professional longevity. The professional burnout of teachers is a huge problem in modern education. Professional burnout is a clinical syndrome that the World Health Organization officially included in the 11th International Classification of Diseases (QD85) on January 1, 2022. According to the definition, it is chronic workplace stress that has not been successfully managed. Professional burnout is a severe symptom that leads to job dissatisfaction, absenteeism, disability pension [1], and reduced professional longevity [2]. Research shows that the level of burnout in many professions correlates with the number of days absent from work for various reasons and periods of absence due to illness. Other surveys reveal that employees with high levels of burnout are absent from work for an average of 13.6 days per year, while those with low levels of burnout are absent from work for only 5.4 days. Worsening burnout predicts an increase in the number of absences by 21% and sick days by 9% even after adjusting socio-demographic, work, and health conditions [3].

International organizations, including UNESCO [4], the Council of Europe, and UNICEF, have highlighted the critical need to address professional burnout among teachers to ensure a sustainable and effective educational system. UNESCO has emphasized the importance of teacher well-being as a foundation for creating a safe and supportive educational environment, which is crucial for both teacher retention and student success. On the eve of National Education Day in 2023, UNICEF has drawn attention to the significant challenges posed by professional burnout among teachers. Chronic fatigue, stress, workload, and lack of support are primary causes of burnout, which affects many professional groups, including healthcare workers, psychologists, social workers, and teachers.

UNICEF and its partners have implemented a broad range of interventions aimed at supporting teachers in Poland and other regions. These initiatives include certified online courses on managing stress and burnout, webinars on strengthening mental resilience, and programs for inclusive education and intercultural communication. These efforts are designed to provide teachers with practical strategies and tools for recognizing symptoms of burnout and developing coping mechanisms.

However, the global teacher shortage crisis further exacerbates the challenges faced by the teaching profession, contributing to increased burnout and stress. On World Teachers' Day [5], UNESCO's Director-General Audrey Azoulay called on governments worldwide to enhance their support for teachers, highlighting that the profession is struggling to retain its workforce and attract new talent. UNESCO estimates that 69 million teachers are needed to achieve universal basic education by 2030, with the largest deficits in sub-Saharan Africa and Southern Asia [6].

Lack of training, unattractive working conditions, and inadequate funding undermine the teaching profession and aggravate the global learning crisis. In low-income countries, teachers face overwhelming workloads, with pupil-teacher ratios significantly higher than the global average. For instance, in sub-Saharan Africa, there are 56 pupils per teacher, compared to the global average of 26. This burden is compounded by insufficient training, with many teachers lacking the necessary qualifications to effectively manage their classrooms.

To address these issues, UNESCO advocates for improved working conditions, better salaries, and enhanced training for teachers. Such measures are essential to mitigate professional burnout and ensure a stable, qualified teaching workforce capable of delivering quality education. For example, UNESCO has launched several initiatives:

Global Teacher Campus: A training platform offering courses and resources to enhance teacher skills and qualifications. In Poland, for instance, teachers are encouraged to take advantage of projects aimed at helping them cope with everyday challenges and maintaining their physical and mental well-being. One such initiative is the "How to deal with stress and burnout" online course available on the Learning Passport platform, which offers practical strategies for managing high demands and pressure.

Teacher Task Force: A coalition of governments, international organizations, and civil society working together to address teacher shortages and improve working conditions.

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD): This initiative seeks to enhance teachers competence and confidence, thereby broadening their opportunities to lead healthy and productive lives in harmony with nature [7]. Additionally, it promotes social values, gender equity, and cultural diversity.

Some scholars also noted that the profession of teacher belongs to social professions that accelerate biological and psychological aging [8, 9] and increased professional burnout among teachers leads to a decrease in their professional longevity and early quitting. Professional burnout increases the likelihood that teachers will look for a reason to be absent from the workplace. For higher education employers, increased professional burnout leads to personnel shortages [10]. Scholars claim that the consequences of teacher burnout in higher education institutions are a decrease in efficiency and involvement in project development in the institution. Their ability to be enthusiastic, efficient, and effective is completely lost. Although education is a factor in increasing the productive period of life [11], teachers showing symptoms of burnout continue to work but with less intensity and interest, which can lead to professional and personal deformation when the teacher conducts classes automatically [10].

Psychologists describe three stages of burnout: a) energy depletion or exhaustion; b) increased mental distance from one's job, or feelings of negativism or cynicism related to one's job (detachment); c) decreased job performance or efficacy, i.e., feelings of personal or professional inadequacy, as well as decreased productivity and coping skills [12].

The relationship between professional longevity and various indicators of professional burnout among public and private school teachers was studied in Turkey. Professional commitment is the desire to continue one's career in the same profession, although the positions may vary. It has been shown that depersonalization (a stage of burnout) has a negative effect on some aspects of professional commitment, in particular on emotional and general commitment, while it does not have a significant impact on normative professional commitment [13].

In a recent review of 993 articles from various databases, we concluded that the consequences of burnout can be very severe, including physical, psychological, and occupational. The most common physical consequences are cardiovascular diseases (coronary heart disease) and hospitalization. There are also other risk factors for such diseases as obesity, hyperlipidemia, type 2 diabetes, metabolic syndrome, hypertension, high triglycerides, low cholesterol, etc. The main psychological consequences are insomnia and depressive symptoms. The professional consequences include job dissatisfaction [1].

Such severe consequences pose another scientific question: What are the causes of professional burnout? Most scholars believe that possible reasons for professional burnout for teachers can be combined into one large group: the lack of safety in the educational environment. According to the UNESCO decree, the study of safety and well-being in education is an important area of research through which the human right to well-being is realized. The key role of a safe educational environment is determined by the well-being of the teacher who shapes this environment and ensures the well-being of students. There is research confirming a significant relationship between school safety and teachers' well-being [14].

The psychological safety of the educational environment includes three main components: 1) an attitude towards the educational environment as a structure that allows one to realize oneself, give positive emotions and in which one wants to work; 2) satisfaction with its main characteristics; 3) protection from coercion and abuse from other teachers, administration, parents, and students [15]. We identified factors of professional self-realization of teachers that have negative correlations with indicators of emotional burnout: job satisfaction, activity (initiative), belief in professional success, cooperation with colleagues, self-education, and desire for self-realization [16].

Research conducted on Chinese teachers at various levels (kindergarten teachers, primary and secondary school teachers) found that the relationship between teacher professional identity and

burnout is partially mediated by their work engagement. I.A. Baeva includes engagement in the cognitive component of the safety of the educational environment. Due to involvement in work, the teacher's professional identity has the greatest predictive impact on burnout [17]. Based on the results of a theoretical and empirical study in Lithuania, the main factors influencing the relationship between professional burnout and professional satisfaction are identified, which emphasizes a significant negative connection between professional satisfaction and professional burnout [18]. According to Baeva, professional satisfaction is part of the emotional component of the safety of the educational environment.

Another important area of studying professional burnout is the search for personal resources that increase the professional longevity of specialists [19; 20]. The safety of the professional environment is also called the main resource for professional longevity [21]. A safe educational environment helps prevent the professional burnout of young teachers [22].

Based on the analysis conducted, we formulated the following **objective**: to study the connection between the characteristics of professional burnout of teachers and the components of the safety of the educational environment of a secondary school. This will allow preventing the professional burnout of teachers through the creation of a safe educational environment.

Hypothesis: There is a connection between individual characteristics of professional burnout of teachers and the psychological safety of the educational environment. The higher the safety indicators of the school educational environment, the lower the level of professional burnout.

METHODS

Diagnostic methods

1. The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) [12], adapted in Russia by N.E. Vodopyanova and E.S. Starchenkova. It is intended to measure the main indicators of professional burnout: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced professional accomplishment.

2. I.A. Baeva's method for assessing the safety of the educational environment for teachers [15] which includes three questionnaires.

I. An attitude to the educational environment of the school. The following indicators were assessed:

1) The cognitive component (Does work at school develop the teacher's abilities and professional skills?). An affirmative answer means that the teacher believes that the school develops their abilities and skills. A negative answer shows that it does not develop such skills.

2) The emotional component (What emotions does work at school evoke: positive or negative?). An affirmative answer means that working at school evokes positive emotions. A negative answer shows that it evokes negative emotions.

3) The behavioral component (the lack of intention to leave this school and profession in general). An affirmative answer means that the teacher strives to remain employed at this school and stay in the teaching profession. A negative answer shows that the teacher wants to quit their job and profession in general.

The general attitude towards the educational environment was also assessed as the totality of other indicators.

II. Satisfaction with significant characteristics of the educational environment of the school. Satisfaction was assessed with the following eight indicators:

1. Relationship with teachers;
2. Relationship with students;

3. The opportunity to express one's opinion;
4. Respectful attitude towards oneself;
5. Preservation of personal dignity;
6. The opportunity to ask for help;
7. Ability to show initiative and start an activity;
8. Considering personal problems and difficulties.

General satisfaction was also assessed as the totality of its components.

A positive value of any indicator meant that the teacher was satisfied with this component, and a negative value meant that they were dissatisfied.

III. Protection from psychological abuse. Protection against this phenomenon was assessed using the following five indicators:

1. Public humiliation/insults;
2. Threats;
3. Forcing to do something against one's desire;
4. Ignoring;
5. Unfriendly attitude.

General security was also assessed as the totality of all components. A positive value of any indicator meant that a person felt protected, and a negative value meant that they felt vulnerable.

Respondents

43 female teachers of secondary schools, aged from 19 to 52 years. The average age is 42.2 years. Two randomly selected secondary schools (in Penza and Ufa) were examined, and the data was summarized. The survey was conducted anonymously with the voluntary and informed consent of the respondents.

Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using various statistical methods.

Descriptive statistics, including arithmetic mean and standard deviation, were calculated for each of the assessed variables, providing an overview of the data distribution.

The Pearson correlation coefficient: To explore the relationship between teacher burnout components and indicators of the safety of the educational environment, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated. Correlations were tested for significance.

RESULTS

We studied indicators of professional burnout and the psychological safety of the educational environment for secondary school teachers. The results are presented in table 1.

According to table 1, the main indicators of teachers are mainly within the average values. However, the indicator "emotional exhaustion" is slightly higher than the average level (average level from 16 to 24). The indicator "reduced professional accomplishment" (reverse scale) is also at a high level (30 or less). The security characteristics of the educational environment are positive. The attitude towards the educational environment is positive too. Satisfaction with the main components of the educational environment fluctuates between "Average" and "More likely than not". Protection against abuse fluctuates between "Whatever" and "Rather protected than not".

Table 1

Average indicators of professional burnout and psychological safety of the educational environment for secondary school teachers

Statistics	Burnout indicators			Educational environment security indicators		
	Emotional exhaustion	Depersonalization	Reduced professional accomplishment	Attitude to the educational environment	Satisfaction with significant characteristics	Protection from psychological abuse
Average value	25.5	9.8	36.2	11.81	31.5	54.3
Standard deviation	5.75	3.10	4.47	4.29	4.14	11.40

At the next stage, we assessed the relationship between all indicators of the safety of the educational environment and indicators of professional burnout. The results are demonstrated in tables 2-4.

Table 2

Relationship between indicators of professional burnout and attitude towards the educational environment

	Attitude to the educational environment			
	Total	Cognitive component	Emotional component	Behavioral component
Emotional exhaustion	-0.609**	-0.209	-0.513**	-0.569**
Depersonalization	-0.258	0.11	-0.403*	-0.193
Reduced professional accomplishment	0.304	-0.077	0.414*	0.213

*<0.05; **<0.01

As can be seen from table 2, the correlation between emotional exhaustion and general attitude towards the educational environment is negative. The worse the teacher’s attitude towards the educational environment of their school, the faster emotional exhaustion develops. The emotional and behavioral components of the attitude towards the educational environment also correlate with emotional exhaustion. The emotional component correlates with depersonalization and reduced professional accomplishment. In other words, if there are any symptoms of professional burnout, the teacher stops enjoying their job. The behavioral component (one’s intention to quit their job) correlates only with emotional exhaustion. The cognitive component (the idea of work as a way of self-realization) is not associated with any indicators of professional burnout.

Table 3

Relationship between indicators of professional burnout and satisfaction with the educational environment

	Satisfaction with the educational environment								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Total
Emotional exhaustion	-0.405*	-0.302	-0.30	-0.716**	-0.548**	-0.275	-0.037	-0.228	-0.533**
Depersonalization	-0.174	-0.247	0.094	-0.395*	-0.201	0.068	-0.170	-0.179	-0.219
Reduced professional accomplishment	0.338*	0.156	0.224	0.389*	0.512**	0.050	0.258	0.053	0.376*

*<0.05; **<0.01

1. Relationship with teachers; 2. Relationship with students; 3. Opportunity to express one’s opinion; 4. Respectful attitude towards oneself; 5. Preservation of personal dignity; 6. Opportunity to ask for help; 7. Ability to show initiative and start an activity; 8. Considering personal problems and difficulties.

As can be seen from table 3, general satisfaction with the educational environment is associated with emotional exhaustion and reduced professional accomplishment. Relationships with colleagues have the most significant connection with the emotional exhaustion of a teacher (such indicators as relationships with teachers, respect for oneself, and preservation of personal dignity). The same indicators are also associated with reduced professional accomplishment. Indeed, this is a symptom complex when real or subjectively perceived disrespect from colleagues leads to diminishing one’s achievements. Depersonalization is not related to a general attitude towards the educational environment but still has one negative correlation with a disrespectful attitude towards oneself.

Table 4

Relationship between indicators of professional burnout and protection from psychological abuse

	Protection from psychological abuse					
	1	2	3	4	5	Total
Emotional exhaustion	-0.348*	-0.479**	-0.326*	-0.272	-0.312	-0.426**
Depersonalization	-0.127	-0.339*	-0.383*	-0.205	-0.238	-0.314
Reduced professional accomplishment	0.383*	0.467**	0.356*	0.293	0.282	0.437**

*<0.05; **<0.01

1. Public humiliation/insults; 2. Threats; 3. Forcing to do something against one’s desire; 4. Ignoring; 5. Unfriendly attitude.

Protection from psychological abuse is associated with reduced professional accomplishment and emotional exhaustion. Considering the components, it is the aggressive characteristics of abuse (public humiliation, threats, coercion to do something against one’s desire) that are associated with indicators of professional burnout. The last two components also increase depersonalization.

DISCUSSION

Establishing relationships between the safety of the educational environment and the professional burnout of teachers allows the psychoprophylaxis and psychocorrection of this syndrome. While professional burnout is a severe clinical syndrome, the safety of the educational environment is a state determined by adjustable and changeable conditions. This study revealed the most significant connections between these two indicators. These are relationships between protection from abuse and all components of professional burnout. They are negative and have a high level of significance. Having examined the patterns identified, we can see that not all characteristics associated with abuse have reliable correlations with professional burnout. Professional burnout is related to threats and coercion to do something against one’s desire, i.e., there is a deprivation of the teacher’s subjectivity (an important factor in modern models of teachers’ professional burnout [23]. We can assume an inverse relationship: if the teacher’s subjectivity, their right to control professional activities and make their own decisions about work increase, this slows down the rate of professional burnout. The results obtained coincide with the data of other surveys analyzed above.

Among all important components of the educational environment, an unsatisfied need for self-respect is closely correlated with professional burnout. Teachers are also dissatisfied with the indicator of personal dignity and their relationships with colleagues. Dissatisfaction concerns interpersonal relationships with colleagues rather than with pupils or parents, about whom teachers more often complain in private conversations. Professional burnout is caused by relationships with

colleagues, the deputy head teacher, and the director, i.e., disrespectful attitude from equal or higher-status colleagues aggravates burnout problems.

The general attitude of teachers towards the educational environment of the school is positive. This attitude is typical of people with high resilience and, according to scholars, slows down biological and psychological aging [24]. If we look at the components and evaluate their relationship with professional burnout, we can notice a striking fact. The cognitive component of teachers' attitudes towards their educational institution is high, i.e., the referent significance of their professional environment for teachers is not reduced. They believe that working at school requires constant improvement of their skills and promotes the development of their abilities. Perhaps that is why there is no correlation between the cognitive component of the attitude of teachers towards the educational environment and professional burnout. The emotional component is low and there are correlations with all components of professional burnout. Teachers do not like their job, it often puts them in a bad mood, and they do not consider it interesting and exciting. The less positive emotions they have at the school, the stronger their professional burnout. However, the emotional sphere can be corrected. There is a fundamental opportunity to fill the educational environment of a secondary school with positive emotions (for example, training using virtual reality technologies [25]). As it is known, reducing the level of professional burnout prevents the occurrence of depressive symptoms [26].

Recommendations. Based on our research, we can formulate several important recommendations to ensure a long and successful professional life for teachers. In forming these recommendations, we relied on both the data we obtained and international experience [27; 28]. To prevent professional burnout, we suggest creating a safe educational environment.

Safety is one of the basic human needs. Satisfying this need at the school's educational level will not only make teachers feel better within the educational organization but also prevent the development of professional burnout.

The first direction in preventing professional burnout through the creation of a psychologically safe educational environment involves improving the psychological climate within the team. We recommend organizing more collective events for teachers and conducting socio-psychological training to unite the team. The training should be straightforward and yield positive emotions. This can become an important component of working with teachers to prevent professional burnout and help increase their professional longevity.

The second direction is to enhance the role of psychosocial factors in organizing the educational environment. Many authors have emphasized the role of psychosocial work factors in ensuring psychological safety and reducing the risk of professional burnout [29]. Significant factors such as job demands, job stress, job satisfaction, role clarity, and student demotivation influence professional burnout. To mitigate this condition, it is recommended to address the satisfaction of high demands at work, improve stress management skills, promote job satisfaction strategies, clarify teachers' duties, and use effective teaching methods to motivate students [29]. Overall, managing psychosocial work factors can be a key direction in preventing professional burnout among teachers.

The third direction is ensuring the stability of teachers' positions in the educational environment. Authors often equate safety with stability. Therefore, providing stability and prosperity for teachers is crucial for their psychological well-being [30]. Ensuring a teacher's stability in the educational environment encompasses several components: professional stability assures teachers of a stable future job; financial stability ensures they receive adequate financial compensation; housing stability guarantees they have a stable living space to rest and recuperate. The administration of the institution is responsible for ensuring the stability of teachers' existence within the educational environment.

CONCLUSIONS

This research established a connection between indicators of professional burnout of teachers and the safety of the educational environment of the school. A decrease in the safety of the educational environment for a teacher leads to the development of symptoms of emotional exhaustion and

reduced professional accomplishment. The symptom of depersonalization is almost unrelated to insecurity. Professional burnout is most aggravated by the teacher's unsatisfactory relationships with colleagues and superiors, and by forcing them to act against their will through threats. Teachers are also dissatisfied with their relationships with colleagues and the emotional atmosphere in their team. Failure to meet these needs correlates with professional burnout.

Research prospects. Our hypothesis was confirmed: the safety of the educational environment can become a resource for the professional longevity of teachers. To attain this end, it is necessary to increase the subjectivity of teachers and their ability to express their opinions and make decisions regarding their activities. This can slow down the rate of professional burnout and contribute to increasing professional longevity.

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